

Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand

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ABSTRACT: This paper aimed to study 1) Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand With the quantitative method, the questionnaire covered 400 samples of Thai Elderly Tourists with non-probability and accidental sampling. Then, the data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the respondent's information and with the correlation and multiple regression to find out any concordances between the strategies and the hotels' success. The research indicated that 1) for the whole of the strategies, Accommodate (X_2) ($\beta = 0.325$, $\alpha < .01$) and Staff (X_3) ($\beta = 0.417$, $\alpha < .05$) had a statistically significant effect on the hotels' success, respectively.

KEYWORDS - strategy hotel; Thai Elderly;

I. INTRODUCTION

Forecasts from the United Nations indicate that the world population in the future will be moving towards a society of The statistics will increase from 687.9 million in 2006 to 1,968 million in 2050. The elderly population in Asia will be The most (Social Research Institute Chiang Mai University, 2014) for in Thailand, the elderly are The number of people increased to 14.1 million in 2023, which means that Thailand will become a "society.[1]

The tourism industry is an industry with high growth. And generate income into Thailand as A large amount of such growth has affected the country's economic and social system as Thailand has Beautiful natural resources Has a cultural identity Traditions and way of life, including Have service potential Which is an opportunity to create tourism value It also affects growth. Of the labor market And distribution of prosperity to every region of the country [2] With And due to the social structure change with the increasing elderly people, the tourism industry Thai people have adapted to accommodate this change by targeting tourism target groups for Elderly tourists Which has a tourism model that focuses on creating quality experiences Profound Within tourist attractions Want to absorb, learn and create spiritual values for tourists Through activities Travel related to life, culture or nature [3] The elderly tourists are the most important tourist groups. One of the most important groups of the world Due to the increasing rate They are quick and have the power to spend on tourism. If considering the classification of tourists in groups The elderly, [4] provided information on the grouping of tourists. A variety of elderly groups such as [5] Has divided the elderly tourists into 3 groups Namely, 1) tourists for leisure, 2) tourists for long-term vacations, and 3) tourists. For health, [6] divided the elderly tourists into 3 groups according to the type of travel. 1) Groups that travel to visit relatives and acquaintances (Family Travelers) 2) Groups who like to plan their travel in advance. They like to do a variety of activities while traveling (Active Resters) and 3) groups that buy travel programs on a package basis [6] At present, Thailand has begun to focus on the elderly. Because in the future it is predicted that Thailand will have an aging population. The elderly in Thailand will account for 32.1% of the nation's population, or about 20.5 million people in the year 2040. It can be seen that the aging society has become closer to Thai people. Compared to traditional Japanese society, public buildings that are designed for the elderly are inevitable with hotels or accommodations for the elderly.

Most hotels offer a wide variety of activities for travelers of various ages. The design that takes into account the elderly is very important and should be realized because in the future the elderly population will be

one-fourth of the Thai population In today's world, countries Turned to study and realized the change of way The structure of the population in entering the aging society is an issue that is of great interest.Both at the national and global level Because it has widespread impact on the macro level such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Income per capita Savings And investment in the government budget Employment and labor productivity Also at the micro level Including the impact on various markets, products and services Especially in finance and health Preparation to support such changes It is an urgent matter for Important to Make a systematic plan and start working Advance Due to various measures Many respects But it takes time to implement to see tangible results.

As a result, hotel operators in Thailand have to strategies to reflect market trends and changing tourist behaviors. It is interested in doing research on Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand to be a guideline for the development of cooperation in the tourism industry for hotel Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand business operators and to build confidence in Elderly foreign tourists.

II. OBJECTIVES/RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The objectives of this research article were to study Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The framework of this quantitative research is based on related concepts and theories to study Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand with details as follows.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of this study

Research Methodology

Population and sample group

The population was Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand. The sample group consisted of 400 respondents by non-probability sampling and accidental sampling. The number was obtained by calculating the formula without the population at a 95% confidence level, and the sample size was set as follows

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{E^2}$$

Where:

n = Size of the sample group

Z = Reliability level

P = Proportion of the population

E = Highest error value which will happen

The acceptance level was in accordance with the statistical significance level at 0.5

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2(0.5)(1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$= 384.16$$

The sample size was 385 respondents. However, 400 questionnaires were gathered by using a probabilistic sampling method between August - December 2020.

Research Instrument

The research tool was a questionnaire where the samples were asked individually to provide information about Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand. The content consisted of 3 parts as follows.

Part 1: General information of the respondents, namely gender, age, and average monthly income

Part 2: Information on factors used in the analysis of Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand.

Part 3: Information on the concordance between the strategies and the set of results to the Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand.

Data analyses

The data were collected by distributing questionnaires in the form of filling in information online to provide convenience and speed to comply with the situation of the COVID-19 outbreak.

The quantitative data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the concordance between the strategies and the set of results to Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand by analyzing the correlation coefficient and stepwise multiple regression.

IV. RESULTS

Regarding general data of the respondents, the following were found:

For the general information of the respondents, it was found that 220 respondents, 60%, were female, and 180, 40%, were male. 187 respondents were between 60-65 years old, 43.50%. 137 of them were 66 - 70 years, 18.50%. There were 35 respondents aged 75-80 years, 17.50%, and were 28 respondents aged 81-85 years, 14%. For the age 85 and over, there were 13 respondents, 6.50%.

Most of the informants, For average monthly income, most of them had an average monthly income of 300,001 - 400,000 baht, 183, 41.50%. There were 40 respondents, 20%, who got 200,000 baht or more average monthly income. For 600,001 - 800,000 baht average monthly income, 128 respondents, 14%, were involved. There were 21 respondents, 10.5%, who got 500,000 - 600,001 baht average monthly income. For the respondents who got less than 700,000 baht average monthly income, it was 7, 3.5%.

The results of the analysis of Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand.

The marketing strategies that affected the success of Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand. The hotel business in Thailand as a whole were Accommodate (X_2) ($\beta = 0.325$, $\alpha < .01$) and Staff (X_3) ($\beta = 0.417$, $\alpha < .05$) with a statistically significant effect, respectively. They could jointly describe the variance of the Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand by 62.1% ($R^2 = 0.621$) and the forecasting equations for the marketing strategies that affected the success of the Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand. Among Thailand on the whole (Y) in standardized form was $Z_y = 0.325ZX_2 + 0.417ZX_3$ Results of analysis of Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand to increase income from other channels

Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand terms of cost retardation, it was found that Promotion (X_3) ($\beta = 0.417$, $\alpha < .01$) affected the Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand with statistically significance. It could jointly explain the variance of the marketing strategy that affected the s Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand by 62.1% ($R^2 = 0.621$), and the equation for forecasting Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand that affected the success of Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand the hotel business in Thailand term of cost retardation (Y) in standardized form was $ZY_2 = 0.621ZX_3$.

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results revealed that overall Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand that affected the success of the Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand with statistical significance was Accommodate (X_2) ($\beta = 0.325$, $\alpha < .01$) and Staff (X_2) ($\beta = 0.417$, $\alpha < .05$), respectively. The variance of the marketing strategy that affected the success of the Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand was 62.1% ($R^2 = 0.621$), and the equation for forecasting Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand the success of the Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand the whole (Y) in the form of a standard score was $Z_y = 0.325ZX_2 + 0.417ZX_3$. This was

consistent with the concept of [7] that strategy referred to Accommodation planning For the elderly It consists of 5 aspects of need: Physical Needs, Shopping, Medical Needs, Home Maintenance, Social and Emotional Needs It was consistent with the idea of [8] that Elderly tourists want something Convenient For example, the number of blankets, handrails in the bathroom, the font size at the hotel.Larger than usual on information materials or signs [9] The nature of the tourism needs for It is divided into 4 areas: 1) health, 2) food, 3) accommodation, and 4) management of travel companies Addition Problems and obstacles in And the operation of tourism business development for For the elderly, 4 major problems were found. Namely, 1) problems from the health of the elderly, depending on the age range, including physical and mental health; 3) The problem from the guide still lacked understanding of the specific characteristics of the service to the group. Of the elderly and 4) problems related to health care services [10] Management of things And facilitating the hotel for elderly tourism in Thailand Issues at the hotel Should be taken into account in the management of The needs of the elderly are different from other tourist groups. In areas 1) physical, 2) health, and 3) social and emotional. And management of things Of convenience according to the concept Civil architecture Take into account the 7 design aspects: 1) equality 2) flexibility 3) ease of design 4) Safety, 5) Space, 6) Understanding, and 7) Help saving.

III. CONCLUSION

Increasing the number of the elderly population in Thailand Had a direct positive impact on management Tourism business For the elderly group because elderly tourists will have different styles and patterns. Tourism behavior that differs from other tourists is the emphasis on tourism and services that are Good quality, good value. Buying for reasons, not emotions. Satisfaction is the key. Long time, high cost Have the ability to purchase services at high prices Because there was money saved from working hard The whole life has a high potential for consumption, while taking into account the confidence of safety. Confident in service Caring for good health Choose activities that are suitable for your age and health Also This group of travelers do not have to worry about their travel expenses. Because they have experience in using Life is more prudent when choosing products and services. Elderly people often have There are more restrictions on travel than young adults. Therefore, the preparation for To support this market, it needs to be studied in quite detail. And there should be good preparation.In the future, the number of elderly tourists will increase. This group of travelers have access to money and time.Travel Hotel operator Therefore, there is a need for adjustment to accommodate more tourists. By Improve and develop things To provide various facilities within their own hotel in accordance with the concept of civilization And meet the accommodation standards for tourism in the 1-5 star category to accommodate older tourists.

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